

International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research Transactions

(A Peer Reviewed Journal)

www.ijmrt.in

Online Educational Process in Educational Institutes for Quality Improvement

Dr. R.D. Jadhav¹, Dr. Anil Gaikwad^{2*}

¹ Associate Professor, Head Dept. of Management, Bharati Vidyapeeth Deemed to be University, Institute of Management Kolhapur, Pune, India.

² Associate Professor, Head Dept. of Computer Applications, Bharati Vidyapeeth Deemed to be University, Institute of Management Kolhapur, Pune, India.

*Corresponding author

Abstract

The Online education is must in the present situation of the Education sector and the process of online education is already started by many educational Institutes . The Basic infrastructure and various software's are required to implement educational activities in the online mode . activities should be planned well in advance before the starting of the academic year . The Social activities play very important role in making very sound personality of the Students . The basic requirements for online education are reliable supply of electricity, good internet speed , ample hardware and software for using the educational apps and also good expert support from back office.

Keywords: Online Education, Hardware, Software tools, Student Internet, Modem, Firewall.

Subject classification: Management , Quality in Higher Educational Institutes

1. Introduction

Defining quality: a complex and multi-dimensional concept The concept of quality is much disputed in higher education and often used by stakeholders in order to legitimize their specific vision or interests. Two reasons can be given for the difficulties encountered when defining quality in higher education:• There is no consensus on the exact objectives of higher education – although some objectives can be named, such as to produce a qualified

work force, to train people for a career in research, to provide efficient management of the teaching profession, and to enhance life prospects.

Definition: A learning system based on formalized teaching but with the help of electronic resources is known as online learning. While teaching can be based in or out of the classrooms, the use of computers and the Internet forms the major component of online learning. Also termed as E-learning can also be termed as a network enabled transfer of skills and knowledge, and the delivery of education is made to a large number of recipients at the same or different times. Earlier, it was not accepted wholeheartedly as it was assumed that this system lacked the human element required in learning. However, with the rapid progress in technology and the advancement in learning systems, it is now embraced by the masses. The introduction of computers was the basis of this revolution and with the passage of time, as we get hooked to smart phones, tablets, etc, these devices now have an importance place in the classrooms for learning. Books are gradually getting replaced by electronic educational materials like optical discs or pen drives. Knowledge can also be shared via the Internet, which is accessible 24/7.

Online Education -learning has proved to be the best means in the corporate sector, especially when training programs are conducted by MNCs for professionals across the globe and employees are able to acquire important skills while sitting in a board room, or by having seminars, which are conducted for employees of the same or the different organizations under one roof. The schools which use E-learning technologies are a step ahead of those which still have the traditional approach towards learning. We have to motivate educational Institutes to use online educational platforms for various educational activities and provide quality education to the students.

Figure.1. Importance of Education to the Students Community

Importance of technology in education are as given below:

1. Simplifies access to educational resources
2. Improves the learning experience
3. Allows students to learn at their own pace
4. Improves research skills
5. Supports reasoning skills
6. Improves self-confidence by helping students acquire new tools
7. Breaks down the barriers to education

2. Various Online Activities that can be Implemented

It's the foremost preliminary step for proceeding with any Social activity for the benefit of the students in the colleges which will make them self sufficient in all the walks of life. The personality will be all-round and society will be benefited by these activities. Following are the main activities.

1. Environmental Protection related activities.
2. Social Health Related Activities.
3. Women empowerment activities
4. Agriculture Related Activities.
5. Village Development Activities.
6. Child Development Activities.
7. Resource management Activities.
8. Financial management Activities.
9. Road Safety and Traffic Management .

10. Curbing Social Issues and Problems like Dowry, Child Marriage

2.1. Challenges faced by Online learning for the students

- **No standard material:** Every time, a class is delivered, the content and presentation of the subject matter change because of the limitations of the teacher.
- **Geographic barriers:** Quality of education depends on the geographical locations of students and their access to local schools.
- **Not personalized:** Education is delivered en-masse with little chance of personalization or customization.
- **Cost and quality:** It is expensive to hire teachers. There might also be a shortage of talented and efficient teachers.

2.2. Solutions Provided By Online Learning:

- All students are given access to standard material, which they can access anytime or from anywhere.
- All students wherever they are located can use e-learning to get access to superior learning material. Geographical dispersion of students is not a problem.
- Students of all backgrounds can access education of top quality.
- E-learning enable students to learn at their individual pace and subjects of their choice.
- The cost of e-learning is minimal when compared to cost of setting up a classroom or hiring teachers. E-learning also gives students chance to learn from the best teachers.
- E-learning includes use of animation. Animation can help make lessons interesting and attractive. Students are able to retain course material in a better way. It helps to make tough concepts simple and will be remembered for a long time.

3. Benefits of Online Education

The time and other resources are used in best way in online learning environment by the students and teachers.

Figure.2. Online Education Platform

3.1. Benefits of AI for Education

Educational apps can be utilized by two types of users — students and teachers. Of course, such solutions bring different benefits to them.

3.2. Advantages of AI in Education for Students

Education at any time. Young people spend a lot of time on the go. They prefer doing everyday tasks using their smart phones or tablets. AI-based applications provide an opportunity to study in free time, spending ten or fifteen minutes. Additionally, the students can get feedback from tutors in a real-time mode.

Various options due to the students' needs. AI-based solutions can adapt due to the students' level of knowledge, interesting topics, and so on. The system tends to help students with their weak sides. It offers learning materials based on their weaknesses. For example, the student does the test before starting to use the app; the app analyzes it and provides suitable tasks and courses.

Virtual mentors. AI-based platforms offer virtual mentors to track the students' progress. Of course, only human teachers can understand the scholars' needs better, but it's good to get instant feedback from the virtual tutor.

4. Quality Improvements in Higher Educational Institutes

The Social and extracurricular activities as stated above are more beneficial to the students and it is going to improve the quality of education at higher educational Institutes'. Following

are the criteria which will be used to find out the quality of the higher educational Institutes suggested by NAAC

4.1. Online Educational Activites

There are various activities that can be performed during the academic year of the Institute:

- College Admission Process
- College Fees portal
- Student Administration
- Attendance Management
- College Examination
- Integration
- E- Learning
- Website
- Purchase & Stores
- Hostel
- HRMS
- Finance
- Library
- Training & Placement

4.2. Resources for Online Learning

In general, when taking an online degree program you might encounter resources like:

- EBooks;
- Journals;
- Videos;
- Recorded lectures;
- Quizzes;
- Discussion forums
- Live Q&A sessions; and
- Interviews.

5. Conclusion

The Online learning has become the need of the hour for the higher educational sector since the students community are now looking for the various advanced modes of learning tools and get the maximum benefits of the education process. The colleges have to update the system so that we can use this technology for the quality improvement of the educational system as whole. This will be very useful to make the colleges update their infrastructure to provide online learning facilities for the students at the college level education. All the stakeholders of education will be benefited by such activities at college level. The proper planning and implementation of these online activities has to be carried out by the management of the Colleges and proper documentation has to be prepared. The innovation in the online learning activities is must to get maximum benefit.

Acknowledgment

The Author is thankful to Management of Bharati Vidyapeeth for motivating in writing this paper for the cause of academics. We are also thankful to authors whose references are used here..

REFERENCES

- [1] A.S. Bames "The Organization and Administration of Extra Curricular Activities Amazon.com pp 67-68 -2015.
- [2] Anil Gaikwad "Role of NSS in colleges" International Conference proceedings SIMCA-2016 Pune pp5-6.
- [3] Borodin, A.; El-Yaniv, R. (1998). *Online Computation and Competitive Analysis*. Cambridge University Press. ISBN 0-521-56392-5.
- [4] Don Slater (2002). "Social Relationships and Identity On-line and Off-line". In Leah; Sonia; Lievrouw; Livingstone (eds.). *Handbook of New Media: Social Shaping and Consequences of ICTs*. Sage Publications Inc. pp. 533–543.
- [5] Rosabeth Moss Kanter (2001). "Introduction". *Evolve: Succeeding in the digital culture of tomorrow*. Harvard Business School. ISBN 1-57851-439-8.

Biography

Dr. R. D Jadhav is Working as Associate Professor in Bharati Vidyapeeth Deemed to University,Pune Institute of Management Kolhapur. He has 25 years of teaching Experience to MBA Classes .He is Head Department of Management.

Dr R.D. Jadhav

Dr. Anil T Gaikwad is Working as Associate Professor in Bharati Vidyapeeth Deemed to be University , Pune. Institute of Management Kolhapur since 1996. He is Head in Department of Computer Applications.

Dr. Anil Gaikwad